

FERGANA PROVINCE DURING THE YEARS OF SOVIET AUTHORITY ON THE ACTIVITY OF MUSIC SCHOOLS

Nargizakhan O.

Alimova Fergana State University
associate professor, (PhD).

M.Khoshimova

Student of FerSu

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Abstract: For the further development of music and art in Uzbekistan, it is important to train real talents who work hard in this field. It is the main task of music schools to provide primary knowledge to such talented people. In this regard, studying the activities of music schools, focusing public attention on their achievements and existing problems will be the basis for future achievements in the art of music.

Key words: Soviet government, music schools, People's Conservatory, free musicianship,

The reforms being carried out in this regard in Uzbekistan serve the further development of culture, especially music. A lot of attention is paid to schools related to music and industry. Also, the importance of historical experience in the development of music is increasing. Studying the activities of schools related to music and the field from a historical point of view, serves to understand its essence, to give important conclusions for today's era. In-depth study is especially important in the cross-section of regions.

In 1920-1921, music schools operated in the cities of Kattakorgan, Samarkand, Namangan, Tashkent, Andijan, Skobelev (Fergana) in Uzbekistan. Music teachers and freelance musicians were trained in music schools. In 1925, 451 students were educated in music education institutions in Uzbekistan, and 65 teachers taught them. The established music schools mainly corresponded to Tashkent, Khorezm, Samarkand and Bukhara regions.

The People's Conservatory was opened in Fergana in 1918, where teachers such as Chernikovsky, Frey, Keizer, Rakhalsky, O.F. Melnikova taught. Among them were pianist and conductor Keizer, violinist Frey, cellist Katana. Fergana People's Conservatory closes by 1920 and many talented musicians go elsewhere.

By the 30s of the 20th century, in order to eliminate the shortage of personnel in musical education, which was considered the most urgent problem, music schools were opened in Fergana region. In 1938, the first music school in

the Fergana region, the Kokan city children's music school (now the 5th BMSM) was founded. In the early stages of this music school, 50 pedagogues-employees served.

In 1939, the 1st children's music school started its activity in the city of Fergana. Also, 1959 Margilan Children's Music School (now 8th BMSM), 1960 20th Children's Music School in Uchkoprik District, 1961 3rd Children's Music School in Ferghana, and 16th Children's Music School in Baghdad children's music school, 14th children's music school in Altariq district in 1963, 6th children's music school in Ko'kan city and 21st children's music school in Rishton district in 1965. In the 1960-1961 academic year, 7 music schools operated in Fergana region, they were music schools of Fergana, Kokhan, Margilan, and Kuvasoi cities. Also, from 1967 to 1972, music schools started working in Beshariq, Toshlo, Kuva, Fergana, Dangara, Yozyovon districts.

There were 5 directions in the first established music schools. They have lessons in the following areas, in particular, piano, violin, cello, bayan-accordion, concert band, and folk instruments. For example, in the 1960-1961 academic year, education was provided in 6 directions in the 2nd music school of Fergana city. In particular, a total of 52 students studied piano. There were also 29 students in the accordion class. Also, a total of 12 students studied in the class of Uzbek folk musical instruments. A total of 1 student studied in oboe class.

The problem of personnel shortage in music education schools was relevant even in the 60s of the 20th century. Especially in this regard, the weight of representatives of the local population, as well as female pedagogues, remained low in the field. In 1961, a total of 2 highly educated female pedagogues worked in music schools in Fergana region. As you know, only 37 of the 63 teachers with secondary education are women. In 1940, the number of highly educated pedagogues in Fargona regional music schools was 4. In 1960, the number of highly educated pedagogues in Fargona regional music schools was 11.

Most of the buildings allocated to music schools were rented. Only the building of the Kokan city music school was given to him. In 1961, a total of 1483 students studied at 7 music schools in the region in 6 directions.

The Kokan city music school was in the first place in terms of coverage. In 1961, 410 students studied at this music school. 344 students studied at the 1st music school of Fergana city.

In the music schools that operated during the years of Soviet power, the number of students was mainly in the fields of piano, violin, bayan-accordion.

Only 12 of the total 168 students studied Uzbek folk instruments at the Kuvasoy city music school. These figures indicate that during the Soviet period, music schools did not pay attention to nationality in the educational process. The main emphasis is on absorbing European music. The same situation is clearly visible in the composition of personnel.

In the 60s of the 20th century, the main part of the teaching staff in music schools was composed of representatives of the Russian-speaking population. For example, 1 out of 20 pedagogues with secondary and special education working in the 1st music school of Fergana city belongs to the local nationality. In the music school in Kokan, only 2 out of 10 secondary-special pedagogues were Uzbeks.

This situation in the composition of personnel has had a negative impact on the scope of national music education. Local children are not sufficiently involved in music schools.

Music schools were originally established as part of the public education system. Music schools were transferred to the management of culture departments in 1951-1960. From September 1960, it was transferred from the Ministry of Culture to the Ministry of Education.

In the 1963-1964 academic year in Fergana region, 148 teachers taught 1930 students in 6 music schools. Only 1 of the teachers was a specialist with higher education. 11 of them had incomplete higher education, 103 had secondary education, and 33 had incomplete secondary education.

The number of young people expressing their desire to study at music schools has been increasing year by year. By 1969, the number of music schools in the region increased to 16. For example, 3 (music schools 1-2-3) in Fergana city, 2 (music schools 1-2) in Kokan city, 2 (music schools 1-2) in Margilan city, Kuvasoy, were music schools in Beshariq, Rishton, Altariq, Baghdad, Kuva districts.

In 1981, 20 7-year music schools were operating in Fergana region. In particular, 1st and 2nd, 3rd music schools in Fergana region, music schools in Kokan, Kuvasoi, Margilon, Baghdad, Altariq, Buvaida, Kirovsky (Beshariq), Kuva, Kuva, Rishton, Tasloq, Uchko. These include music schools in the districts of Prik, Uzbekistan, Fergana (Avval), Dangara, and Yoyovon.

By the 80s of the 20th century, more than 200 7-year schools specializing in music, 2 11-year special music schools and 20 music institutes were operating in the entire musical education system of Uzbekistan.

Since the end of the 60s of the 20th century, the number of young people of the local population in the scope of music schools has increased. By the 80s of the 20th century, the coverage of music schools was increasing, music clubs were opened even under village soviets, and school students were widely involved.

During the years of Soviet power, European trends were forcefully promoted in music schools. Despite extensive propaganda and propaganda in this regard, national melodies and songs have not lost their essence. No matter how hard they tried, the tunes and songs that were instilled and ordered by the current government did not become popular among the population. The people of our country have never stopped being creative. Therefore, famous music was created, popularized and became a masterpiece of the people in the same years.

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